

TREAT-AD

TaRget Enablement to Accelerate
Therapy Development for AD

ECE1 (endothelin converting enzyme 1)

A Target Enabling Package (TEP)

Gene ID / UniProt ID / EC	1889/ P42892
Target Nominator	TREAT-AD
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TARGET SOURCE & HYPOTHESIS

Why was the target selected? This target is found within a TMT proteomics network module that was highly correlated with cognition. This module (Module 42) contains several novel AD targets, including SMOC1 and SFRP1.

TREAT-AD Target Risk Score: 3.90 (rank #558, 97.8th percentile)

The TREAT-AD Center has developed a target ranking score encompassing genomics and genetics evidence. The Target Risk Score represents the gene target’s general relevance to Alzheimer’s Disease, and is the sum of the target’s Genetics Score and Genomics Score. Target Risk Score values range from 0 to 5, with 5 being evidence of the strongest association with AD. A complete description of the methodology used to calculate these scores is available [here](#). This score was taken from Agora, Data Version syn13363290-v62.

The TREAT-AD Target Risk Score for this target is 3.90 out of 5 (rank #558, 97.8th percentile). The individual score components include 1.91 of 3 for genetics, and 1.99 out of 2 for genomics. The meta-analysis of proteomic and transcriptomic data sources used in the genomics score indicates that the expression of ECE1 protein and RNA is significantly increased in brains from patients with AD.

The TREAT-AD Center has also developed a target categorization system specific to AD relevant processes, termed biological domains (biodomains). These biological domains are defined by constituent Gene Ontology (GO) terms and genes are then annotated to specific biological domains via GO term annotations. ECE1 is annotated to GO terms from 6 different biodomains, primarily to terms from the Endolysosome, Proteostasis, Synapse, and Metal Binding and Homeostasis domains.

Overall	rank	pctl	GeneticsScore	OmicsScore
3.899	558	97.76	1.913	1.986

Cell-type specific expression is assessed using single-cell expression data from the Allen Brain Institute. The distribution of expression values for all genes found in each broad cell type are displayed as violins, points indicating the expression of the target in specific subtypes within each broad class including a label for the highest expressing cell type for each broad class. These data indicate that ECE1 is expressed in vascular and leptomenigeal cells

(VLMC), endothelial cells, astrocytes, oligodendrocytes, and both excitatory and inhibitory neurons in this dataset.

SUMMARY OF PROJECT

Endothelial converting enzyme 1 (ECE1) is an activating peptidase that converts endothelin zymogen into the active signaling peptide (1), driving vasoconstriction within arterial endothelial cells (2). In brain, ECE1 degrades nascent amyloid, and may regulate amyloid levels of the most toxic soluble oligomer (3-5). However, little is known about the role of ECE1 specifically in therapeutically treating AD. The goal of this work is to produce a basic target enabling package (TEP) that will consist of the bioinformatics workup discussed above, identified and functionally validated antibodies and purified protein. The public dissemination of these resources will hopefully promote further investigation into the potential role of ECE1 in treating AD.

SCIENTIFIC BACKGROUND

Endothelial Converting Enzyme 1 (ECE1) is a peptidase involved in the conversion of endothelin from an inactive precursor to the mature endothelin signaling peptide, which associates with multiple Gq-coupled receptors that activate PLCgamma and increase intracellular calcium levels (1, 6). ECE1 expression is high in multiple cell types in brain, as demonstrated in the cell-type distributions noted above, including endothelial cells and astrocytes. The TREAT-AD bioinformatics analysis demonstrates AD risk derived from both the multiomic and genetic portions of the score to similar degrees. A genetic association with disease is observed for ECE1, being associated with Hirschsprung's disease, autonomic dysfunction and cardiac disease. Interestingly, in brain, ECE1 activation of endothelin is associated with vasoconstriction of small arterial vessels (2, 7). Over two decades ago, ECE1 was identified as a broader peptidase that also is involved in the degradation of amyloid (5), which is the primary association for ECE1 with Alzheimer's disease (AD). ECE1 is part of the neprilysin family of amyloid degrading peptidases, which also includes insulin degrading enzyme (IDE) (4, 8). The plausible role in AD was identified as ECE1 expression is increased in AD brain, likely as a compensatory response to disease pathology(9), suggesting a role in amyloid proteostasis. The decline of ECE1 and other amyloid degrading enzymes may be promoted by damage associated with oxidative damage (10). The notion that ECE1 plays a role in regulating amyloid clearance was further supported by studies showing that genetic deletion of ECE1 increases amyloid in both cellular neuronal and mouse models of AD (11). Expanding on these observations, it was later observed that ECE1 appears to degrade amyloid produced specifically within the endosomal pathway in cellular and mouse models(12, 13), suggesting that locally produced amyloid via endolysosomal complexes associated with synapses may be the site of ECE1 action (12), arguing against a distributed systemic model of amyloid regulation(3, 12). Members of the neprilysin family may coordinately regulate or compensate for the absence of any one member (3, 4, 14-16), supporting a class role in amyloid proteostatic regulation. In TREAT-AD proteomic studies, ECE1 was identified as part of module 42 (M42), a module that is highly correlated with AD pathology and negatively correlated with cognitive performance (17). These studies suggest that ECE1 may play a role in amyloid clearance in the brain, and potentially to resilience to AD pathology.

RESULTS – THE TEP

Validated Antibodies & Generic Knockout Cell Lines

The YCharOS Antibody Characterization Report guides researchers to select the most appropriate antibodies for ECE1. The YCharOS antibody characterization pipeline uses knockout (KO) cells to perform head-to-head comparisons of available commercial antibodies for ECE1 by immunoblot (Western blot),

immunoprecipitation and immunofluorescence. The cell line background was chosen based on the adequate expression of the target protein.

[Complete report: ECE1 Antibody Characterization Report](#)

Proteins Purified

1. ECE1_101-770_HisN_AviC. The extracellular domain of human ECE1 (residue range 101-770) with N-terminal honeybee melittin signal peptide for insect cells secretion followed by 6HisTag and a TEV cleavage site, and a C-terminal AviTag (for in vitro biotinylation).

See **Additional information (section 1)** with details of plasmid expression constructs and purification procedures.

CONCLUSION

The tools presented here provide a foundation for further investigation of the role of ECE1 in AD.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The work performed by the Emory-Sage-SGC TREAT-AD Center has been funded by the National Institute on Aging through grant U54 AG065187.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Materials and Methods

1. Protein expression constructs and protein purification

All relevant plasmids are available on addgene: [TREAT-AD plasmid collection](#)

1. ECE1_101-770_HisN_AviC

UniverGene name	ECE1
Uniprot ID	P42892
Region	101-770

Description	Converts big endothelin-1 to endothelin-1.
Synonyms	Endothelin-converting enzyme 1
Construct ID	ECE1_101-770_HisN_AviC PBC040D07
Parental Vector	pFHMSP-AviN-LIC-N
Tag (N-terminal)	MKFLVNVALVFMVVYISYIYAAAPEHHHHHHHDYDIPTTENLYFQGAMD
Tag (C-terminal)	SSKGGYGLNDIFEAQKIEWHE
Protein mass (with tag)	84420.23 Da
Extinction Coefficient with tag ($M^{-1} cm^{-1}$)	143295
Protein sequence (with tag)	MKFLVNVALVFMVVYISYIYAAAPEHHHHHHHDYDIPTTENLYFQGAMDSEACVSVTSSILSSMDPTVDPCHDFFS YACGGWIKANPVPDGHRSRWGTFNSLWEHNQAIKHLLNSTASVSEAERKAQVYRACMNETRIELRAKPLM ELIERLGGWNITGPWAKDNFQDTLQVVTAHYRTSPFFSVVVSADSKNSNSNVIQVDQSGGLPSRDYLYLNKTEN EKVLTGYLNYMVQLGKLLGGGDEEAIKQILDFETALANITIPQEKRRDEELIYHKVTAELQTLAPAINWLP FLNTIFYPVEINESEPIVVYDKEYLEQISTLINTTDRCLLNNYMIWNLVRKTSFLDQRFQDADEKFMVEMYGTTK TCLPRWKFCVSDTENNLFALGPMFVKATFAEDSKSIATEIILEIKKAFEESSLTKWMDDETRKSAKEKADAIYN MIGYPNFIMDPKELDKVFNDYTAVPDLYFENAMRFFNFSWRVTADQLRKAPNRDQWSMTPPMVNAYYSPTK NEIVFPAGILQAPFYTRSSPKALNFGGIGVVVGHETHAFDDQGREYDKDGNLRPWVKNSSVEAFKRQTECMV EQYSNYSVNGEPVNGRHTLGENIADNGGLKAAAYRAYQNWVKKNGAEHSLPTLGLTNNQLFFLGAQVWCSVR TPESSEGLITDPHSPSRFRVIGSLSNSKEFSEHFRCPPGSPMNPCHKCEVWSSKGGYGLNDIFEAQKIEWHE

Purified Protein	
Affinity purification, Ni-NTA (step 1):	<p>From 8L culture 2ml beads/L culture for each run Tris 8.0 500 NaCl 5% glycerol/250 imidazole</p>
ECE1_101-770_HisN_AviC	

<p>Size Exclusion Chromatography (step 2):</p> <p>ECE1_101-770_HisN_AviC</p>	
<p>Ion Exchange chromatography (step 3)</p> <p>ECE1_101-770_HisN_AviC</p>	
<p>Intact Mass Deconvolution:</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Observed Mass:</p>	<p>N/A</p>
<p>Protein yield:</p>	<p>0.6 mg/L of culture</p>

<p>Expression and Purification Protocol</p>	
<p>Expression host</p>	<p>Insect cells: Sf9 (<i>Spodoptera frugiperda</i>)</p>
<p>Expression Medium</p>	<p>I-Max Insect Media W/ L-Glutamine, Wisent Biocentre</p>
<p>Transformation and storage</p>	<p>The baculovirus expression vector system (BEVS), specifically Bac-to-Bac Expression System (Invitrogen), employing <i>Autographa californica</i> multiple nucleopolyhedrovirus (AcMNPV) has been used for expression screening and production of target protein. The plasmid transfer vector containing the gene of interest was transformed into DH10Bac <i>E. coli</i> competent cells to generate recombinant viral bacmid DNA. Adherent Sf9 cells were then transfected with bacmid DNA to generate recombinant viruses used for the baculovirus-mediated production in the insect cells.</p>
<p>Expression</p>	<p>For the scale-up productions, suspension cultures of the baculovirus-infected insect cells, (SCBIIC) were prepared by infection of the Sf9 cells with the corresponding P2 viruses. On the day of production, 2 L of Sf9 cells (cell viability > 97%) in 2.5 L Tunair shake flasks or 4 L in 5 L reagent bottles were diluted to a cell density of 4×10^6 /mL. These cells were infected directly with 10-12 mL/L of suspension culture of baculovirus-infected insect cells and incubated at a lowered temperature of 25 °C, at 145 rpm. Infected cells' density and viability along with the cell sizes monitored after 72 hours post-infection time to be able to collect cells for purification at the optimal conditions when Sf9 cells are well infected, usually in 5-6 days after the post-infection time.</p>

Purification buffers	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Lysis buffer: 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 1 mM TCEP 2. Elution Buffer (EB): 50 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 500 mM NaCl, 5% glycerol, 250 mM imidazole 3. SEC buffer: 20 mM Tris (pH 8.0), 150 mM NaCl, 2mM TCEP 4. IEC buffer: 20 mM Tris (pH 7.5), 1M NaCl, 5. Ni-NTA beads, equilibrated in the Lysis buffer.
Purification step 1: Ni-NTA	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Spin down cells @6500RPM for 15min 2. Transfer each 1.5L supernatant to a 2.8L flask with 150ml 10X PBS. 3. Add (2ml/L) Ni-sepharose beads to the supernatant and shake at 100RPM at 18 °C for 60 min. 4. Transfer the supernatant + beads to an open column to collect the beads and keep the flowthrough. 5. Wash beads with 50CV of lysis buffer. 6. Elute protein with 5CV elution buffer. Analyze the EB fractions by SDS-PAGE and determine the protein yield using the Bradford assay. 7. Add beads (2ml /L) to the collected flowthrough for the second binding same condition and repeat the same wash and elution after 1hour shaking.
Purification step 2: Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Purify the protein further by Size-exclusion chromatography (SEC) on a HiLoad Superdex S200 26/60 column in SEC buffer at 3 ml/min. 2. Analyse fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity for the next step.
Purification step 3: Ion Exchange chromatography (IEX)	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Purify the protein further by Source Q, anion exchange chromatography. 2. Elute with concentration gradient of 20 mM Tris (pH 7.5), 1 M NaCl (buffer B). 3. Analyse fractions by SDS-PAGE. Pool fractions containing protein of desired purity and concentrate to 8.6 mg/ml, as measured by UV spectroscopy. <p>Snap-freeze aliquots in PCR tubes in liquid Nitrogen, and store at -80°C.</p>

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